

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

РАЗРАБОТКА НОВОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ ДЛЯ ЛОКАЛЬНО-ПРИНУДИТЕЛЬНОГО ОСАЖДЕНИЯ ЖИДКИХ ПЕСТИЦИДОВ В ОБРАБАТЫВАЕМОЙ ОБЪЕКТ

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DEVELOPMENT OF NEW TECHNOLOGY AND TECHNICAL MEANS FOR LOCAL AND FORCED DEPOSITION OF LIQUID PESTICIDES IN THE PROCESSED OBJECT

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена разработке новой технологии и технических средства для локально - принудительного осаждения жидких пестицидов в обрабатываемой объект. В статье обоснована актуальность предлагаемой технологии и перспективность технических средств, даны технологические схемы имеющие большие технологические, экологические и экономические возможности, которые защищены патентами и ряд ученых работающих в сфере защиты растений.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of a new technology and technical means for the local forced introduction of liquid pesticides into the processed object. The article substantiates the relevance of the proposed technology and the prospects of technical means, presents technological schemes with great technological, environmental and economic opportunities, which are protected by patents and a number of scientists working in the field of plant protection.

Ключевые слова: разработка, технология, технического средства, локальный, принудительный, осаждение, жидкость, пестицид, почва.

Keywords: development, technology, technical means, local, forced, deposition, liquid, pesticide, soil.

Introduction: The purpose of this work is to substantiate and develop technology and technical means for locally forced deposition of liquid pesticides into soil, seed material and plants, with the use of which:

- prevents pollution of the environment, soil and groundwater from liquid pesticides;
- the liquid chemical is evenly distributed in the treated area;
- the quality indicators of the use of liquid pesticides are increasing;

- the degree of destruction of harmful organisms increases;

- the economic indicators of the use of liquid pesticides are increasing;

- the mechanism of chemical influence of the use of liquid pesticides increases.

According to a number of studies [1..7], it is known that plant protection is an integral part of crop production technologies. It is impossible to overestimate the role of chemical plant protection products, which at one time contributed to the success of the

"green revolution" and allowed to abruptly increase the yield of various crops. Despite the importance of resistant varieties and hybrids, agrotechnical, biological and other methods of reducing the number of harmful organisms, chemical plant protection cannot be replaced by any other method either today or in the near future. And the practice of agricultural production has convincingly shown this.[8] The use of chemical plant protection products in agro-ecosystems, making it possible to significantly increase the productivity of agricultural crops, at the same time has an adverse effect on biotic and abiotic elements of agroecosystems that cause risks of chemical pollution [9].

The effectiveness of plant protection measures largely depends on the technical condition of the spraying equipment and the reliability of the technological spraying process. Therefore, in a number of European countries (Germany, the Netherlands, Denmark, Hungary, Belgium, Poland), mandatory technical inspection of spraying equipment is carried out for the right

of operation, and in Switzerland, Sweden, Norway, Finland this is done on a voluntary basis.

The technical inspection provides for checking the operability of the drive, pump, hydraulic agitator, lifting and unfolding mechanisms of the rod sections, the tightness of the main and auxiliary tanks, connecting and pressure fittings of the hydraulic system of the sprayer, the quality of the spray nozzles, the operation of fans, shut-off devices, the serviceability of control and measuring equipment.[10]

Theoretical and experimental studies concerning the local-forced method and means of mechanization for the introduction of pesticides allowed to justify the apply of herbicides into the soil:

- form and parameters is a cross section that is made in the form of an arc of a circle formed in the soil for uniform distribution of liquid chemicals on the inner surface; (fig. 1....3)

Fig.1.

Laboratory installation for determining the distribution of the working fluid on the inner surface of the furrow

Fig.2. Calculated schemes for spraying pesticides on a flat-rectilinear section and on a semicircular furrow with radius R: a) spraying on a flat-rectilinear section; b) spraying on the inner surface of a semicircular furrow with radius R.

Fig.3. Calculation scheme for comparing the technologies of spraying pistidides of a liquid preparative state on a flat-rectilinear and on the inner surface of a semicircular furrow with radius R : a_i [l] i [a] i respectively, the angle between the droplets coming out of the tip and the distance between these droplets on a spherical and plane-parallel plane.

- constructive parameters and operating modes of the device for automatic regulation of the rate of liquid chemicals (continuous and batch application) during sowing; (Fig.4,5)

Fig.4. Technological scheme of the device for automatic regulation of the working fluid: 1 is fixed regulator plate; 2; 3 are link; 4 is load; 5 is chain transmission; 6 is islitter; 7 is movable plate; 8- U is shaped part; 9 is bearing; 10- is gate; 11 is housing gate; 12 is spring; 13; 14 are nut; 15; 16 are pair of screw nut; 17 is tank; 18 is pump; 19; 20; 21 are pipe

Fig.5. Technological scheme of the device for automatic control of the flow rate of chemical preparations during local (during sowing) spraying: 1 is the shaft of the sowing disc; 2 is the sowing disc; 3 is the hole of the sowing disc; 4 is the regulating coupling; 5 is the shutter rod; 6 is the support wheel of the sower; 7 is the chain; 8 is fixed plate; 15 is rack; 9 is nut; 10 is link; 11 is load; 12 is spring; 13 is pinch; 14 is movable plate; 15 is rack; 16 is gate; 17 is distributor housing; 18 is the outlet of the housing; 19 is the housing cover; 20 is the inlet of the housing; 21 is the axial space of the shutter; 22 is the radial channel of the shutter; 23 is seal.

There is increasing interest both here and abroad in the use of UAVs - a variety of unmanned aerial vehicles, as a rule, aircraft (with a non-movable wing) or helicopter (with one or more rotors) type. Currently, small-sized UAVs with a small flight weight (up to 30 kg) are widely used when conducting survey flights and monitoring various objects, including agricultural and

forest lands. Unfortunately, for today, the practical possibility of using UAVs for the aviation distribution of various substances in the interests of agriculture, forestry and utilities has not been sufficiently studied.[11;12;13]

- forms and parameters of technical means for the forced deposition of droplets on the surface of soil and plants located in the space after spraying; (Fig. 6,7)

Fig.6. Device for the forced deposition of the working mixture on the surface of plants prepared from an iron rod and fabric, which is attached to the sprayer during spraying of agricultural plants: 1 is coating to direct the air flow during the movement of the sprayer; 2; 3 are side coating; 4 is rear coating; 5 is top coating.

Fig.7. Technical means for the forced deposition of pesticides on the surface of cultivated plants: 1-a thin sheet; 2 is a guide for adjusting its position relative to the horizontal axis of the sheet; 3 is a support; 4; 7 are a link; 5 is a litter; 6 is a rod; 8 is a spraying tip; 9 is a tape; 10 is a side leaf; 11 is a cultivated plant.

- the forms and parameters of the sprayer rod for spraying leaves, plant shoots from below and above separately and simultaneously

Fig.8. Technological scheme of the proposed new sprayer of trunks and leaves from above and (or) from below plants: 1 is handle; 2 is liquid distributor of the rotating plugging type; 3; 4 are horizontal and vertical pipe of the rod; 5; 6 are device for ensuring movement along and around the axis of the tip of the sprayer equipped with a screw pair; 7; 8 are spraying tip; 9 is device for axial movement along the horizontal pipe of the rod; 10; 11; 12 are hose α , β , γ , respectively, the angle of spraying, the angles of rotation of the tip in the frontal and vertical planes. elow and above separately and simultaneously; (fig. 8).

- forms, parameters and elements of a wick device for contact destruction of weeds having a height greater than the height of the cultivated plant; (fig.9)

Fig.9. New wick device (technological scheme)

a) general view; b) the position of the wick meeting with the weed: 1 is stand; 2 is herbicide tank; 3 is wick; 4 is spring; 5 is hinge; 6 is cultivated plant; 7 is weed; 8 is filter; 9 is rod.

In the fight against harmful insects and mites during grain storage, two groups of chemicals are most widely used are gaseous and liquid

The disadvantages of this method include the fact that after degassing (gas removal), the grain or the room are not protected from repeated pest infestation [14]

Etching is rightfully considered one of the main techniques in the technologies of pre-sowing seed preparation, it has a multiple payback and increases the overall profitability of agricultural production.[15,16,]

Processing of seed material of grain crops with protectants or mixtures thereof is a mandatory technique. For its implementation, both domestic and foreign manufacturers supply seed protectants with a capacity of up to 20 t/h.

The basic technological schemes of the machines ensure the performance of two main operations: first, a working fluid (RJ) water + a protectant is prepared in a tank with a capacity of up to 300 liters, then it is pumped into the seed etching chamber. The etched seeds are fed by an unloading transporter to the seeder tanker for delivery to the seeder units in the field or to the closed-flow site

The most widespread in the Russian Federation were the picklers of domestic (PS-10AM, PS-22, PS-20K-4) and imported production - PSK-15 (Belarus) and PK-2002 "Super" (Ukraine). A common disadvantage of these machines is the increased material and

energy intensity of the process of preparing the working fluid in a tank with a capacity of 200-300 liters, and the absence of a mechanical stirrer in the tank PS-20K-4 (JSC Agrohimmash, Stavropol) restricts its operation when using powdery preparations. [17]

The main uses of the Air Force in crop production are a variety of survey flights for the purpose of monitoring, planning and monitoring the condition of agricultural land and the work carried out (creation of electronic maps and inventory of fields, assessment of the condition of crops and the normalized vegetation index NDVI), land cultivation with pesticides and agrochemicals.[18]

Modern resource-saving technologies place particularly high demands on the quality of seed preparation and sowing technologies, since minimizing tillage contributes to the accumulation and survival of phyto pathogens and phytophages in the upper soil layer and on plant residues, which significantly complicate the passage of the most vulnerable period by plants from seed germination to the formation of full shoots [19, 20].

Determined are qualitative indicators of laboratory and field package samples of the proposed technology and technical means during operation with different design parameters and modes of operation are determined ((Fig. 10.14)

Fig.10. Laboratory plant for etching seeds of agricultural plants (technological scheme): 1 is conveyor belt; 2 is conveyor drum; 3 is scavenger; 4; 10 are seeds; 5 is clamping link; 6 is support; 7; 9 are paralon; 8 is dishes

Fig.11. Technical means for etching seeds of agricultural plants: 1 is conveyor belt; 2 is conveyor drum; 3 is guide; 4 is tank; 5 is etching drum with a surface covered with foam; 6 is etching drum shaft; 7 is foam tape; 8 is dishes; 9 is link; 10 is rack; 11 is electric motor; 12 is chain drive; 13 is bolt

Fig.12. The calculated scheme of the device for feeding the lowered cotton seeds into the etching zone: 1- conveyor belt; 2-a disk with a surface covered with foam.

Fig.13. Technological scheme of the "AZETBMI" device for etching dropped cotton seeds: 1 is conveyor belt; 2 is conveyor drums; 3 is belt drive; 4 is electric motor; 5 is paralon etcher; 6; 18 is dishes; 7 is spatula; 8; 17 are foam rubber; 9 is revolving conveyor drum; 10; 11 are hopper; 12; 13 are dispenser; 14; 15 are chain drive; 16 is flattener; 19 is etched seeds; 20 is gesture; 21 is bag; 22 is base; 23 is rack; 24 is pipe

Fig.14. Devices for etching seeds of agricultural plants during sowing: 1 is hopper; 2 is seeds; 3 is pipe; 4 is rubber coating; 5 is disc; 6 is foam rubber; 7 is etched seeds; 8 is dishes for the preparation; 9 is tank of liquid mixture.

Conclusion: Experimental studies with batch - nesting and continuous-strip application of liquid chemicals were carried out with norms of 75 l/ha and 250 l/ha, respectively.

The research results showed that:

- with batch and continuous methods of liquid chemical supply along the width of the grip and along the length of the rut, the best indicator is, respectively, 9.1% and 14.1%, 9.7% and 7.2%;

- qualitative indicators of spraying plants in tiers P ...III) from the bottom and top of the leaves of plants is 14, respectively...19% and 31 ...35%:

- the quality indicators of the device for etching the outer surface of the lowered cotton seeds is -97%, with damage prevention.

The annual economic effect from the use of devices for the supply of liquid and dust-like pesticides when sowing watermelon seeds is 9283 and 1477.3 manats, respectively, adaptations to the mass-produced unit OPSCH-15 for spraying the surface of plants with a pesticide is 38421.6 manats, devices for etching the surface of lowered cotton seeds with liquid fungicides against pests and diseases is 2998 manats.

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